

PROCESS OPTIMISATION FOR MILLING CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITE MATERIAL USING RESPONSE SURFACE METHODOLOGY AND VIBRATION ANALYSIS

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1 Abstract

Optimal conditions for milling carbon/epoxy composite material were established by response surface methodology. The combination of cutting parameters such as cutting speed (V_c) and chip thickness (h) was varied at design points of a central composite design. Significant regression models describing the changes of vibration level, delamination of composite, cutting force, workpiece temperature were developed with the coefficient of determination greater than 0.90. Results suggested that beyond a threshold of vibration, the occurrence of delamination is regular. Vibration criterium was defined from the observations of the workpiece according to the delamination defect. The optimum milling conditions were achieved by means of graphical techniques using design contour plots. The best combination of process variables was found according to the cutting conditions.

2 Introduction

The use of composite parts, especially in aeronautics, is increasing at an exponential rate. However, machining of this material is complicated due to different phenomena such as delamination.

Different authors such as [1-4] have concluded that cutting conditions are a significant factor in determining tool life and machining cost. Lasota and Rusek [5] described the influence of cutting conditions on energy consumption during finish turning. The cutting process may negatively impact the properties of the materials as reported by Ghidossi et al. [6]. Studies related to the machining of fiber-reinforced polymer composites have been published by many authors such as [7-10]. Authors highlighted the fact that the heterogeneity of the cutting material and poor choice of cutting conditions could not only generate premature cutting tool wear [11], but also cause severe damage to the workpiece [12]. The most common defects encountered during composite machining are delamination, fiber pullout and resin overheat. In order to understand the machining defects, some authors have linked the cutting conditions to damage [13]. Koplev et al. [14] and Ramulu [15] have shown that the carbon fibers orientation is a relevant factor in explaining cutting edge failure and material defects. In the work of Rawat and Attita [16], machinability maps have been introduced in drilling. This method includes several quality measurements at the end of the process, such as delamination defects, hole circularity and surface quality. Piquet et al. [17] noted that if the temperature reaches or exceeds the glass transition

temperature, the composite workpiece can cause local damage to the epoxy matrix. When the resin is affected by high temperature, it can become rubbery and stick to the cutting edge of the cutting tool. Guegan et al. [18] and Arola and Ramulu [19], mention that surface roughness easily impacts results, and different fiber orientations could induce high measurement error. Therefore, it may be possible to use vibration analysis to characterize the machining quality without proceeding to undependable quality measurements. Jang et al. [20] developed an online real-time monitoring algorithm for controlling a machine in a flexible manufacturing system, using the cutting vibrations created by contact between tool and workpiece. Dimarogonas and Haddad [21] noted that vibrations are highly undesirable because they adversely affect the surface quality, limit the dimensional accuracy of a workpiece, lead to higher tool wear rates, create high levels of noise and could result in damage to the machining tool itself or to the spindle. In addition, experiments have been carried out by Mer and Diniz [22] to monitor the change of surface roughness of the workpiece, caused by increasing tool wear, through the variation of vibration in finish turning experiments. The results showed that tool vibration can be a good method for online monitoring of the increase in surface roughness.

Response surface methodology (RSM) is an effective technique for developing, improving, and optimizing processes. It is often used to combine several independent variables and assess the effect of their complex interactions on desired responses. RSM uses statistical Design of Experiment (DOE) techniques, such as the central composite design (CCD) and least squares fit in the model generation phase. The performance of the proposed model is then demonstrated using checking tests provided by the analysis of variance. Response surface plots can be used to investigate the results and

determine the optimum condition. A number of authors have used statistical methods (RMS, Taguchi and DOE) to evaluate manufacturing operations efficiency when machining composite materials [23-25]. Morandea et al. [26] have made a comparative study in terms of cutting force, workpiece temperature and tool wear for different configurations of tool when machining carbon/epoxy composite.

The aim of this study is to present a new technique for selecting the optimal cutting conditions through the correlation of vibration levels, workpiece temperature and cutting force with defects generation during machining of the carbon/epoxy type T800S/M21 composite material. This technique was presented by Chibane et al. [27] for PCD cutting tool considering only the vibration levels as a parameter for determining delamination. CCD was used to minimize the number of experimental data. Regression analysis was used to build the relationships between composite workpiece vibration (A_{rms}), maximum cutting force (F_{max}), workpiece temperature (T) and machining parameters such as cutting speed (V_c) and chip thickness (h). Variance analysis was used to prove/validate the model.

3 Design of experiments

Design of Experiments is a powerful tool for analyzing the influence of process variables on some specific variables. Appropriate data can be analyzed by statistical methods such as RSM and MLR. Statistical validation of experimental design is necessary to draw meaningful conclusions from data [28].

An effective alternative to the composite factorial design is the Central Composite Design, originally developed by Box and Wilson [29], and improved by Box and Hunter [30]. CCD gives as much information as a tree level factorial design, requiring a lower number of tests than the latter, and describes a majority

of steady-state process responses. For two parameters ($n=2$), CCD can be represented in space by points on a cube shape. Each cube axis corresponds to a factor and each point represents an experiment, consisting of 2^n factor points, $2n$ axial points and tree center points (tree replications). The upper limit of a factor was coded as +1.21, and the lower limit as -1.21, these values were used to calculate the machining parameters.

Response Surface Methodology explores the relationships between several explanatory variables Y and one or more response variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n as given in Eq. (1) the experimental error is represented by Φ . The goal is to optimize the response [31]

$$Y = \Phi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \pm e_r \quad (1)$$

The second-order model demonstrates the second-order effect of each variable, separately, and the two-way interaction between combinations of these variables. This second-order mathematical model can be represented as follows:

$$Y = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n b_i x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n b_{ii} x_i^2 + \sum_{i < j} b_{ij} x_i x_j + r_e \quad (2)$$

Where b_0 represents the linear effect of x_i , b_{ii} represents the quadratic effect of x_i and b_{ij} reveals the linear-by-linear interaction between x_i and x_j .

In order to estimate the regression coefficients, a several experimental design plan are available.

4 Experimental details

Down milling tests were performed on a horizontal high speed milling machine PCI METEOR 10 HSK63A (spindle speed $N_{max}=24000$ rpm, Power $P=40$ kW). The multi-axial composite carbon/epoxy T800S/M21 was machined with a single Diamond Like Carbon

(DLC) insert provided by the cutting tool manufacturer [32] as shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1. Cutting tool with the insert [32]

The orientation of the composite plies is described by $[(45/90/135/0)_{16}]_s$ with ply thickness equal to 0.26 mm as illustrated in Fig.2. Dry machining conditions were used during the experimental tests.

Fig.2. Structure of the composite material T800S/M21

A wide range of cutting conditions was tested with a depth of cut equals to four plies in order to minimize the influence of plies orientation.

To minimize the number of experiments, a central composite design (CCD) with 9 combinations was studied, using parameters

such as cutting speed (V_c) and chip thickness (h) as shown in Fig.3.

Vibration analysis of the workpiece for each cutting condition was used. Note that the central test was repeated 3 times, and the average value is shown in the following figure:

Fig.3. Central composite design of experiment

The levels of machining parameters were chosen in accordance with the recommendations provided by the cutting tool manufacturer [32] and [9] as shown in Table 1.

Fig.4. Experimental set-up of the workpiece and position of accelerometer

The radial engagement (a_e) of the cutting tool into the material was 36.4 mm. Vibration levels (A_{rms}), delamination length (L_d), workpiece temperature (T) and cutting force (F_{max}) were measured for each test in one pass.

Variables level	Cutting speed (m/min)	Chip thickness (mm)
Min (-1.21)	96	0.06
Min (-1)	200	0.1
Mean (0)	450	0.2
Max (+1)	700	0.3
Max (+1.21)	803	0.34

Table 1. Machining parameters levels

Vibrations were measured using a tri-axial accelerometer (Brüel & Kjær 4520) mounted on the workpiece (Fig. 4). The sensitivity of the accelerometer in the x , y and z directions were 1.032, 1.067 and 1.047 mV/g, respectively. A multianalyzer (Brüel & Kjær 3560) was connected to a computer for recording temporal data using Pulse Labshop software. The duration of the signal was same as the duration of machining with sampled frequency equal to 65536 Hz. Signal processing was performed using MATLAB Environment. RMS (Root Mean Square) acceleration was calculated (using the time signal of the vibration) for each test. To take into account the composite fiber orientation, the average RMS vibration measured in the 3 directions x , y and z was determined according to the following equation:

$$A_{rms} = \sqrt{A_{x_{rms}}^2 + A_{y_{rms}}^2 + A_{z_{rms}}^2} \quad (3)$$

Delamination is one of the most critical defects during machining of composites, since it causes elevated vibration levels which may decrease the life of a composite structure significantly. To use composites to their full capacity, it is necessary to analyze the initiation and development of delamination. Regarding ply

delamination, a superficial observation was done in the initial point of contact for machining, using an optical microscope. Fig.5 shows the profile of two machining tests, with and without delamination.

Fig.5. Profile of workpiece during two machining tests, (a) test 1 with delamination, (b) test 9 without delamination

Other defects such as epoxy resin burnt, was observed. Epoxy resin burnt occurs if the workpiece temperature exceeds 150°C. Due to difficulties in monitoring temperature in the chip formation region, it was decided to observe milling surface at the precise instant when the mill ended the machining step. Fig.6 shows the experimental set-up of measuring workpiece temperature of the composite part by an infrared camera during machining.

Fig.6. Measuring workpiece temperature by an infrared camera during machining

Cutting force investigation leads to understand the cutting mechanism.

As the case of vibration level, cutting force was measured for each test in the 3 directions x , y and z , and the mean value was determined according to the following equation:

$$F_{\max} = \sqrt{F_{\max}^2 x^2 + F_{\max}^2 y^2 + F_{\max}^2 z^2} \quad (4)$$

These frame transformations are applied to the mill in order to observe the force intensity and direction on the cutting edge.

To integrate the productivity in the choice of cutting parameters, the material removal rate (MRR) was calculated for each test by the relation:

$$MRR = \sqrt{\frac{ap \times f \times Vc \times a_e \times z}{\pi \times d}} \quad (5)$$

Where Z is the number of teeth ($Z = 1$) and d is the cutting tool diameter ($d = 72.8$ mm). The objective considered was to increase the material removal rate to increase productivity. The experiment variables are summarized in table 1.

N°	V_c m/min	h mm	A_{rms} m/s ²	L_d mm	T °C	F_{max} N	MRR cm ³ /min
1	96.5	0.2	54.06	0	98	70	134.56
2	200	0.1	50.95	0	74	54	136.98
3	200	0.3	81.77	0	67	89	237.27
4	450	0.06	68.87	0	151	54	159.16
5	450	0.2	114.41	1.9	153	99	290.59
6	450	0.34	103.39	1	95	104	378.89
7	700	0.1	154.10	3	315	100	256.28
8	700	0.3	176.12	3.66	206	113	443.89
9	803.5	0.2	205.71	4.6	285	142	388.30

Table 2. Summary table of measures

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Model fitting

The combined effects of cutting speed and chip thickness on vibration levels, delamination length, workpiece temperature and cutting force are presented in Table 2.

Table 3 shows the coefficients of variables in the models calculated by the least square technique. The table also summarizes the statistical parameters, namely the determination coefficient (R^2), adjusted determination coefficient (R^2_{adj}) and F-test probability, both of which are used for measuring the correlation and significance of the models.

Regression	A_{rms} (m/s ²)	L_d (mm)	T (°C)	F_{max} (N)
Constant	-29.26	-2.67	-17.43	-24.95
V_c	0.08	0	0.22	0.09
h	658.51	25.2	734.13	691.5
$V_c \times V_c$	0	0	0	0
$h \times h$	-1228	-63.94	-1301	-1108
$V_c \times h$	-0.09	0	-1.02	-0.22
R^2	0.989	0.99	0.97	0.96
R^2_{adj}	0.972	0.97	0.92	0.91
$F\text{-test prob}$	0.002	0.003	0.017	0.02

Table 3. Models parameters

Results of the R^2 values showed a good agreement between experimental data and predicted data for all regressions (0.98, 0.99, 0.97 and 0.96 for vibration levels, delamination length, workpiece temperature and cutting force, respectively). The results of the F-test showed a statistically significant relationship between the variables within a 95% confidence interval.

5.2 Model of vibration level and delamination

length

Results show that beyond a threshold of vibration, the occurrence of delamination is regular and increases with increase in the levels of vibration (Fig.7).

Fig.7. Threshold of vibration level and limit of delamination

The result shows that in tests 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9, delamination was observed with a vibration level value greater than 100 m/s² (Fig. 7). The vibration threshold was defined as follows: among the tests with no defect, the one with maximum vibration was selected (test 3). This test was defined as the minimum value of the uncertainty region. The uncertainty region was calculated from the tree duplicate tests and evaluated at ± 5 m/s².

Regions with and without defects were defined from the vibration model, taking into account the level of vibration.

These regions help the operator to choose cutting parameter values (cutting speed, depth of cut and feed rate) in order to avoid delamination.

Vibration criterium was defined from the observations of the workpiece according to the delamination defect.

The response surface methodology was used to determine the analytical model which expresses the vibration level and the delamination length according to the cutting parameters (cutting speed and chip thickness).

Fig. 8(a) and 8(b) shows the vibration level contour and delamination length, respectively. It is clear that vibration increases with increasing feed rate and depth of cut.

Fig.8. graph contour of vibration level (a) and delamination length (b) as a function of cutting speed and chip thickness

Fig 9 gives a 3D surface graph for vibration level and the delamination length respectively according to the cutting parameters (cutting speed and chip thickness).

Fig.9. Response surface graph of vibration level (a) and delamination length (b) as a function of cutting speed and chip thickness

A clear similarity between the vibration level and the length of delamination is observed. This similarity is confirmed by the iso-values and response surfaces of the two models shown in figures 8 et 9. This confirms the correlation between the level of vibration and the presence of delamination.

5.3 Model of workpiece temperature

Regression factors linked to this model were used to build the relationship between the workpiece temperature and the two study parameters as shown in table 2. The coefficient of determination R^2 equals 0.92. That is, 92 %

of the variation in temperature fits with the model while 8% cannot be explained. The model is more significant if this coefficient approaches 1. This coefficient indicates that the workpiece temperature measurements satisfy the model used.

In order to determine the significance of the model, variance analysis (ANOVA) was used as shown in Table 3. The Fisher test shows that the F-probability is lower than 0.017 (Prob > F), indicating that the independent variable gives enough information for the model.

The profile for workpiece temperature with respect to the cutting speed and chip thickness is shown in Fig. 10. It is clear that the workpiece temperature increases with increase in corresponding cutting speed and chip thickness.

Fig.10. Response surface graph for temperature as a function of cutting speed and chip thickness

5.4 Model of cutting force

The regression factors linked to this model were used to build the relationship between the cutting force and the two study parameters as shown in table 2. The coefficient of determination R^2 equals 0.97. That is, 97 % of the variation in cutting force fits with the model while 3% cannot be explained. This coefficient indicates that the cutting force measurements satisfy the model used.

The Fisher test shows that the F-probability is lower than 0.02 (Prob > F), indicating that the independent variable gives enough information for the model.

The evolution of cutting force is shown with respect to cutting speed and chip thickness in Fig.11.

Fig.11. Response surface graph for cutting force as a function of cutting speed and chip thickness

6 Optimisation of cutting conditions

A graphical multi-response optimisation technique was adopted to determine the workable optimum conditions for milling composite material. The contour plots for all responses were superimposed and regions that best satisfied all the constraints were selected as optimum conditions. The main criterion for constraints optimisation was maximum possible for production (material removal rate) and lowest vibration level, workpiece temperature, delamination and cutting force. These constraints resulted in a “optimal zone” of the optimum solutions (shaded area in the superimposed contour plots). Superimposed contour plots, having common superimposed area for all responses for cutting process.

Therefore, the criteria applied for the graphical optimisation were $T < 150^\circ$ (temperature of epoxy resin burnt), $F_{max} < 97$ N (over this effort

the delamination was observed) and $A_{rms} < 100$ m/s² (vibration threshold).

Three configurations of material removal rate were study to approuve the optimisation:

The first configuration is used to select the cutting conditions with a material removal rate higher than 200 cm³/min (Fig. 12). The white region represents the range of operating parameters that does not lead to defects and a productivity of $MRR > 200$ cm³/min.

The corresponding optimum operating conditions for cutting speed and chip thickness were [100, 400] and [0.1, 0.35], respectively.

The second configuration is used to select the cutting conditions with a material removal rate higher than 250 cm³/min (Fig. 12). The white region represents the range of operating parameters that does not lead to defects and a productivity of $MRR > 250$ cm³/min.

The corresponding optimum operating conditions for cutting speed and chip thickness were [200, 400] and [0.15, 0.35], respectively.

The last configuration is used to select the cutting conditions with a material removal rate higher than 300 cm³/min (Fig. 12). The white region represents the range of operating parameters that does not lead to defects and a productivity of $MRR > 300$ cm³/min.

The corresponding optimum operating conditions for cutting speed and chip thickness were [300, 400] and [0.3, 0.35], respectively.

The white area (1, 2 and 3) represents the region produced by the criteria outlined above respectively.

Fig.12. Optimum region identified by the overlaid plots of the responses: T , F_{max} and A_{rms} with: (a) $MRR=200$, (b) $MRR=250$ and (c) $MRR=300$

7 Conclusions

This study is a combination of several methods for detecting machining defects which can be generated on a workpiece made of carbon/epoxy composite. The defects taken into account in this study are: delamination of the composite layers and overheating of the composite matrix. Vibration and cutting force analysis of the workpiece was used for each cutting condition. A threshold of vibration was defined from the observations of the delamination of the workpiece.

The response surface methodology was used to determine the analytical model which relates the level of vibration, cutting force and workpiece temperature to two cutting parameters: cutting speed cutting speed and chip thickness. ANOVA results confirmed that the mathematical models used in this study could adequately describe the performance indicators within the limits of the factors that are being investigated with a 95% confidence interval. The results of the analysis show. This new technique of should help the operator to select the optimum cutting conditions such as cutting speed and feed rate (chip thickness) in order to avoid damage to the carbon/epoxy composite material T800S/M21 and increase machining productivity. To apply this method for different configurations, their corresponding response surface equations and vibration threshold (which depends on the material, machine type, tool, clamping and position of accelerometer), should be defined from the experiment.

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